

Enhancing Human Activity Recognition Through Deep Learning And Object Detection In Video Streams

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Abstract— For the purpose of comprehending human behavior in a variety of fields, such as security, medicine, and human-computer interaction, Human Activity Recognition (HAR) is essential. The enhanced HAR system presented in this work makes use of object detection methods and deep learning techniques. A Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network is trained for activity categorization by preprocessing video data, extracting informative characteristics, and applying the approach. To further improve contextual comprehension during activity recognition, object detection is included to identify pertinent objects in video streams. Tests using the UCF-101 dataset show how well the model recognizes a variety of human activities. By advancing the creation of reliable human-machine interface (HAR) systems, this research advances practical applications.

Keywords— Human Activity Recognition, Deep Learning, LSTM, Video Analysis, Object Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern era, comprehension of human behavior and object detection in movies are essential for a number of applications, such as healthcare, entertainment, and surveillance. The two main components of this study are object detection in films and human activity recognition (HAR). One component of HAR is identifying and classifying various human activities that are portrayed in video sequences. This research attempts to reliably characterize human activities from video footage using deep learning techniques, namely Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. The algorithm gains the ability to accurately recognize different groups of human activities, including basketball, riding, and typing, by using a dataset.

In addition, the research explores Object Detection, a crucial computer vision problem that entails identifying and categorizing things in pictures or videos. YOLO (You Only Look Once) object identification model that has been pre-trained is used here to identify things in video frames. The model can identify items in a scene and offer details about their location and class by examining each frame individually. With the integration of Object Detection and

HAR, this study provides a holistic approach to comprehending human behavior and object identification in films. This method shows promise for improving video analysis applications in a variety of fields, such as security, entertainment, and healthcare, by combining cutting-edge object detection models with deep learning techniques.

A. Using LSTM Networks for HAR

The application of LSTM networks for precisely categorizing human actions in video clips is examined in this section.

B. Object Recognition with the Yolo Model

The application of a pre-trained YOLO (You Only Look Once) model for object detection in video frames is the main topic of this section.

C. Hardware and Object Detection Integration

This section demonstrates how HAR and Object Detection work together to provide a complete solution for comprehending human behavior and recognizing things in films.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) has garnered significant attention due to its diverse applications in healthcare, surveillance, and human-computer interaction. Recent advancements in deep learning techniques have propelled the field, enabling more accurate and robust recognition systems. Uzzaman et al. [1] proposed an LRCN-based approach for HAR from video data, leveraging the capabilities of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks with Convolutional layers. Their work demonstrates promising results in capturing temporal dependencies and spatial features from video sequences, enhancing the accuracy of activity recognition.

In the realm of educational institutions, research into HAR has shown its potential in monitoring and enhancing learning environments. R et al. [2] presented a study on HAR, possibly

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highlighting the role of such systems in educational settings. Although the details of their approach are not specified, their work underscores the growing interest in integrating HAR into diverse applications, including academia.

Object detection remains a cornerstone in computer vision, with YOLO (You Only Look Once) being a pioneering method known for its speed and accuracy. Diwan et al. [3] delved into challenges, architectural successors, datasets, and applications related to YOLO-based object detection. Their comprehensive review provides insights into the evolution of object detection methods and highlights the ongoing efforts to improve detection performance and efficiency.

Advancing the methodologies in HAR, Bhatia et al. [4] proposed an innovative approach combining Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory (ConvLSTM) and LRCN for activity recognition. Their hybrid model aimed to capture both spatial-temporal features, demonstrating the potential of integrating different deep learning architectures to achieve superior performance in HAR tasks.

Lastly, Dewar et al. [5] focused on the application of LRCN in HAR, providing an in-depth exploration of the model's capabilities in recognizing human activities. Their study further validates the effectiveness of LRCN-based approaches, emphasizing the importance of continuous research and development in advancing HAR systems.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In order to correctly classify and comprehend human actions shown in video data, the suggested methodology makes use of Human Activity Recognition (HAR) via Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. The suggested method aims to improve activity recognition and classification by utilizing deep learning and sequential data analysis. This will enable applications in a variety of fields, including sports analytics, healthcare, and surveillance.

The steps required for the proposed model:

1. Data Collection and Preprocessing
2. Dataset Labeling and Organization
3. Model Architecture Design
4. Training the Model
5. Model Evaluation and Validation
6. Testing and Deployment

Data Collection and Preprocessing

Collect video footage of various human activities so that it is represented in a variety of contexts. To ensure consistent input to the model, extract and resize the frames from the movies to standardize their proportions. To improve training efficiency, normalize pixel values.

Dataset Labeling and Organization

Assign activity labels to frame sequences, making sure that every frame sequence corresponds to a human action. Divide the labeled dataset into separate testing, validation, and training sets to provide an objective assessment of the model's performance.

1. *Data Collection* – To train a model, collect a variety of video datasets, extract and resize frames, and normalize pixel values.
2. *Dataset Labeling* – To guarantee objective assessment, allocate activity labels and divide datasets for testing, validation, and training.
3. *Model Architecture Design* – Create a hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture to represent temporal dependency and extract spatial features.
4. *Training the Model* –To avoid overfitting, use regularization techniques when training the CNN-LSTM model.
5. *Model Evaluation and Validation* – Evaluate generality and accuracy on validation data, and make model refinements based on learnings.
6. *Testing and Deployment* – Assess real-world results using previously unseen data and implement for the HAR application.

Figure 1: The human activity recognition model

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1. Import the necessary packages

```
import os
import cv2
import math
import random
import numpy as np
import datetime as dt
import tensorflow as tf
from collections import deque
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from tensorflow.keras.layers import *
from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.utils import to_categorical
from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping
from tensorflow.keras.utils import plot_model
import tensorflow as tf
```

2. Uploading Videos

Users can upload videos through the user interface

Figure 2: Upload Video

3. Prediction Process

The uploaded video is preprocessed, predicted, and the results are seen when prediction starts. Temporary file storage is also done for effective processing.

4. Final result

Figure 3: Output Prediction

V. CONCLUSION

In the created method, the combination of long short-term memory (LSTM) networks and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) demonstrates a strong synergy between these deep learning techniques for human action classification in videos. Through the use of LSTM for temporal modeling and CNNs for spatial feature extraction, the system is able to recognize activities with impressive accuracy. Moreover, the system's capacity to provide real-time predictions is enhanced by the preprocessing of video input and the training of a hybrid CNN-LSTM model, which further increases the system's usefulness in dynamic contexts. This method, when combined with the development of an easy-to-use Streamlit interface, highlights user-friendliness and technological prowess, making it suitable for a broad spectrum of users with different degrees of experience.

This technique could lead to advancements in the field of human activity recognition, which has consequences that go beyond its technological achievements. The technology has potential to meet a variety of societal demands, including those related to surveillance, healthcare monitoring, and human-computer connection. It can identify and categorize human behavior in movies, which offers up possibilities for improved security protocols, customized medical treatments, and user-friendly computer-human interfaces. As such, the established method holds substantial potential to drive breakthroughs in other fields where human activity analysis is critical, in addition to being a major advancement in the field of deep learning.

2. REFERENCES

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